

Supplementary material for:
A graph-based probabilistic geometric deep learning framework
with online enforcement of physical constraints to predict the
criticality of defects in porous materials

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1 Volume and surface mesh

As discussed in section [3.2] of the main paper, the input and output of the model is the surface and not the volume stress. In [Fig. 1] we see an example of a surface stress extracted from the volume mesh. We can observe that the maximum value of the Von Mises stress is the same in both cases and the location where the maximum Von Mises stress occurs is the same as well.

Figure 1: Two structures corresponding to one quarter of a random realisation of the dogbone geometry. In the diagram on the left (a) we see the Von Mises stress distribution on the volume mesh. In the diagram on the right (b) we see the Von Mises stress distribution on the surface mesh. We can see, in the red circles, that the maximum values in both structures are in the same location.

2 GNN parameters and architectural choices

We identified some key parameters for the training of the GNN and performed several tests to identify their optimum values. The parameters that we examined is the number of filters in the MLPs, the number of GN Blocks, the number of maximum neighbours per node, the existence of a skip connection between the input and the output of the network and finally the type of encoder. For these tests we used 500 patches as the training set and 100 patches for the test set.

2.1 Skip Connection

We suggest that using a skip connection to add the input macroscale stress tensor to the output of the network will improve GNN’s performance. The reason behind this is that the GNN will learn how the microscale stress field deviates from the macroscale stress field instead of learning the microscale stress field from zero which we believe that it is easier and it should also improve the generalization ability of the network. In order to validate our assumption we train 2 identical GNNs with the exact same parameters and training set but one of them has a skip connection and the other does not. Both networks have MLPs with 128 filters, 10 GN blocks and each node has at most 10 neighbours. The results can be found in [Fig 2] where we can observe that the GNN trained with the skip connection has smoother convergence compared to the GNN trained without the skip connection. Also, the skip connection improved accuracy from 65% to 80%. We conclude that indeed the skip connection helped not only to have more stable training but also to improve the accuracy and thus we decide to include it in our architecture.

Figure 2: In the diagram we see accuracy curves for the test dataset defined using the maximum Von Mises stress. The yellow line corresponds to a GNN trained with a skip connection to add the input macroscale stress to the output of the GNN and the blue line corresponds to a GNN trained without this skip connection. We observe that the skip connection results in smoother training and higher accuracy.

2.2 Number of Filters

An important parameter that heavily influences not only the accuracy of the GNN but also the training time and memory requirements is the number of filters in the MLPs. In order to identify the minimum number of filters that result in optimum accuracy we trained 3 GNNs with 64, 128 and 256 filters in the MLPs and we kept all the other parameters the same. Specifically, all networks have the skip connection described in [2.1], 10 GN blocks and each node has at most 10 neighbours. The results can be found in [Fig 3] where we observe that 128 and 256 filters result in the same accuracy which is higher than the accuracy for the 64 filters, 80% compared to 72%. Additionally, the training time for the GNN with the 256 filters is 12.7 hours and the maximum required memory is 15.4 GB while for the 128 filter GNN the training was completed in 5.8 hours and the maximum required memory was 7.7 GB. By choosing to use 128 filters in the MLPs of the GNN we achieve the same accuracy as in the 256 filters GNN but with a 54% decrease in the training time and a 50% decrease in memory requirements.

Figure 3: In the diagram we see accuracy curves for the test dataset defined using the maximum Von Mises stress. Coloured lines correspond to networks trained with different number of filters, namely 64, 128 and 256. We observe that 128 and 256 filters result in the same accuracy 80% where 64 filters result in a lower accuracy of 72%.

2.3 Independent Decoder

As already discussed in section [3.6] of the main paper, in the first layer of the GNN we choose to encode the edge and node features independently into the latent dimension as suggested by [Sanchez-Gonzalez et al., 2020; Pfaff et al., 2021; Mylonas et al., 2022]. We want to test if this choice results in an improved GNN and thus we perform an experiment between 2 GNNs with the same parameters where one uses a GN block to encode the inputs into the latent dimension and the other encodes them independently. Both of the GNNs have 10 GN blocks, 128 filters in the MLPs, the skip connection described in [2.1] and each node has at most 10 neighbours. The results can be found in [Fig 4] where we observe that both GNNs have similar accuracy curves and they both have a final accuracy of 80%. Nevertheless, we can observe that in the independent encoder case the accuracy starts increasing sooner, at epoch 50, where in the GN block case it starts increasing later, at epoch 120. Lastly, the independent encoder version involves slightly less calculations and results in a 5% decrease in training time. Consequently, we choose to use the independent encoder GNN.

Figure 4: In the diagram we see accuracy curves for the test dataset defined using the maximum Von Mises stress. The yellow line corresponds to a GNN trained with an independent encoder and the blue line corresponds to a GNN trained with a GN block as an encoder. We observe that both GNNs have similar accuracy curves with the same final accuracy but the GNN with the independent encoder starts increasing its accuracy sooner, epoch 50, compared to the other one, epoch 120.

2.4 Number of GN blocks

Another important parameter that affects both the memory requirement and the training time is the number of residual GN blocks. Because we are using residual connections we do not expect a decrease in accuracy as we add more GN blocks but we are expecting that there should be a saturation point where the GNN does not benefit anymore from the GN blocks but it performs unnecessary calculations resulting in increased computational cost. To validate this assumption and determine the most proper number of GN blocks we train 3 GNNs with the same parameters but different number of GN blocks. All the GNNs have 128 filters in the MLPs, the skip connection described in [2.1], independent encoder and each node has at most 10 neighbours. The results can be found in [Fig 5] where we observe that the GNN with only 3 GN blocks presents a decrease of 10% in the test accuracy compared to the other two. Also we can see that the GNNs with 5 and 10 GN blocks have similar test accuracy curves and they both reach a test accuracy of 80%. We decide to opt for the GNN with the 5 GN blocks that presents optimum accuracy without additional computational cost. This results in a training time of 3.1 hours and a maximum memory of 4.3 GB which is a decrease of 45% in training time and 44% in memory requirements compared to the GNN with the 10 GN blocks.

Figure 5: In the diagram we see accuracy curves for the test dataset defined using the maximum Von Mises stress. Coloured lines correspond to networks trained with different number of GN blocks, namely 3, 5 and 10. We observe that the GNN with 3 GN blocks has a decreased accuracy compared to the rest. Additionally, we can see that the GNNs trained with 5 and 10 GN blocks have almost exactly the same behaviour.

2.5 Number of neighbours

We want to study the effect of the maximum number of neighbours on the GNN training. A small number of maximum neighbours will result in a graph where disconnected areas of the FE mesh do not share an edge and thus cannot exchange information, for instance microscale and macroscale features. We train 3 GNNs with the same parameters apart from the maximum number of neighbours that have values 5, 10 and 15. All the GNNs have 5 GN blocks, 128 filters in the MLPs, the skip connection described in [2.1] and independent encoder. The results can be found in [Fig 15] where we observe that 10 and 15 neighbours result in the same accuracy which is higher than the accuracy for the 5 neighbours, 81% compared to 75%. Additionally, the training time for the GNN with the 15 neighbours is 27% higher and the memory requirements 31% higher compared to the GNN with 10 neighbours. We conclude that in our case we do not have a reason to use more than 10 neighbours although in denser meshes this number could be different.

Figure 6: In the diagram we see accuracy curves for the test dataset defined using the maximum Von Mises stress. Coloured lines correspond to networks trained with different number of maximum neighbours per node, namely 5, 10 and 15. We observe that 10 and 15 neighbours result in the same accuracy 81% where 5 neighbours result in a lower accuracy 75%.

2.6 Geodesic and Euclidean Convolutions

We study the effect of the joint convolutions by training 6 GNNs with different number of Geodesic and Euclidean filters. We perform the study on the dogbone dataset. We keep the total number of filters constant to 128 but we change the ratio between Geodesic and total (Euclidean + Geodesic) filters. We investigate the case where the ratio is 0% (only Euclidean), 25%, 50% and 75%, 87.5% and 100% (only Geodesic). All the GNNs have 5 GN blocks, residual connection, independent encoder, 128 filters and a maximum of 20 neighbours per node. The results can be found in [Fig 7]. We can observe that both for the accuracy and the loss the worst case is when the ratio is 0, so no Geodesic convolutions are present. Both the accuracy and the loss improve (accuracy increases and loss decreases) as we increase the ratio until the value 75%. After that no further improvement in performance is observed, both the accuracy and loss curves for ratio values 75% and 87.5% are the same. On the contrary when the ratio becomes 1 there is a substantial drop in performance, which is expected since no Euclidean convolutions are performed. We conclude that a 75% ratio is the most beneficial for this case.

Figure 7: In the diagram on the left (a) we see accuracy curves defined using the maximum Von Mises stress and a 15% threshold for the relative error. Specifically, we see the accuracy as function of the training epochs. In the diagram on the right (b) we see the loss function as a function of the epochs. For both diagrams, coloured lines correspond to GNNs trained with different Geodesic to total (Euclidean + Geodesic) filter ratio, namely 0% (only Euclidean), 25%, 50%, 75%, 87.5% and 100% (only Geodesic).

2.7 Full stress field VS maximum stress

We investigate the option to directly predict the maximum Von Mises stress on the surface of the dog-bone structure. To this end, we train 2 identical GNNs on patches extracted from 100 FE simulations and we evaluate them in a different set of patches extracted from 100 FE simulations. One of the GNNs directly predicts the maximum Von Mises stress and the other the full stress tensor. Both GNNs have 5 GN blocks, independent encoder, 128 filters (32 Euclidean and 96 Geodesic) and a maximum of 20 neighbours per node. The results can be found in [Fig 8]. We observe that the 2 GNNs have similar accuracy, but the one predicting the full stress has slightly higher values. We conclude that predicting the full stress is beneficial since it not only results in better prediction of the maximum Von Mises stress but it also provides us with the full stress tensor that can be used for instance for the online bias corrections.

Figure 8: Accuracy curves as a function of the threshold value used for the relative error. The accuracy curves are defined using the maximum Von Mises stress. The blue line corresponds to a GNN that predicts the full microscale stress distribution first and then from this the maximum Von Mises stress in the ROI of the patch. The orange line corresponds to a GNN that directly predicts the maximum Von Mises in the ROI of the patch.

2.8 Patches VS full structure

Lastly, we want to evaluate to what degree our choice to train the GNN using patches of the geometry affects the quality of the results. This choice stems from the fact that defects only locally affect the macroscale stress field and distant areas do not offer significant information. On one hand, training on patches has the benefit of making the GNN unaware of the specific structure and it encourages it to focus on predicting how the microscale features affect the global stress field, thus leading to improved generalisation. On the other hand, our choice for the size of ROI and patch has to be careful so that the network has all the necessary information to make predictions in the ROI. Choosing to train the GNN using the entire structure alleviates us from this problem. We perform an experiment to compare the two strategies. We train two GNNs with the same parameters, namely 5 GN blocks, residual connection, independent encoder, 128 filters (32 Euclidean and 96 Geodesic) and a maximum of 20 neighbours per node. The first one is trained using patches from 400 FE simulations (10 patches from each simulation) and the second one is trained directly on the 400 FE simulation results. We evaluate both GNNs on a separate set of patches extracted from 100 FE simulations. The results can be found in [Fig 9]. We can observe that for the GNN that was trained on patches the maximum Von Mises in the ROI of the patches is less scattered around the $y = x$ line, true value. The coefficient of determination for the patch case is 0.79 compared to 0.71 for the full case and the accuracy significantly drops from 70% for the patch case to 55% for full dogbone case. Thus we conclude that our choice to train the GNN with patches indeed leads to improved generalisation. We also compare the Von Mises stress distribution on the surface of a dogbone predicted by the GNN trained with patches with the GNN trained with the entire structure. In [Fig 10] we see that the GNN that was trained using patches more accurately predicts the high stress area compared to the GNN that was trained with the full structure.

Figure 9: In both diagrams the x-axis corresponds to the maximum Von Mises stress in the ROI of the patches calculated by FE simulations and the y-axis to the maximum Von Mises stress in the ROI of the patches predicted by the GNN. The yellow lines correspond to the 15% relative error threshold. The accuracy is defined as the percentage of points with relative error less than 15%. The image on the left (a) corresponds to a GNN trained with patches extracted by 400 FE simulations and the image on the right (b) to a GNN trained directly on the same 400 FE simulations. We can observe that the GNN trained on patches outperforms the GNN trained on the full structures both in terms of accuracy and coefficient of determination.

Figure 10: Von Mises stress on the surface of a dogbone structure (top). On the bottom of the image we have zoomed in the high stress area. From left to right we see the FE result, the prediction of the GNN trained with patches and the GNN prediction of the GNN trained with full structures. We observe that the GNN that is trained with patches is in better agreement with the FE results compared to the one trained on the full structures.

3 Ensemble Kalman Method: Observation matrix free implementation

We can simplify the calculations involved in the Kalman update procedure by avoiding to explicitly define the observation matrix. Instead we can define a function that will provide the noise free value of the data. This function is called observation function and is of the form

$$h(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x} \quad (1)$$

The posterior can be written as

$$\mathbf{X}^* = \mathbf{X} + \frac{1}{N-1} \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{A})^T \mathbf{P}^{-1} (\mathbf{D} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{X}) \quad (2a)$$

$$\mathbf{H}\mathbf{X} = h(\mathbf{X}) \quad (2b)$$

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{X} - \frac{1}{N} \mathbf{X} \quad (2c)$$

$$\mathbf{H}\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{X} - \frac{1}{N} \mathbf{H}\mathbf{X} \quad (2d)$$

$$\mathbf{P} = \frac{1}{N-1} \mathbf{H}\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{A})^T + \Sigma_\epsilon \quad (2e)$$

4 Dogbone scaled error examples

Below we can compare the GNN prediction with the FEA results in 5 cases. The scaled error seen in the next figures is defined as the absolute difference between the microscale Von Mises stress as calculated by FEA and as predicted by the GNN, divided by the maximum microscale Von Mises stress as calculated by FEA.

Figure 11: Comparison between the microscale Von Mises stress distribution as calculated by FEA (b) and the one predicted by the GNN (c). We can also see the input macroscale Von Mises stress interpolated on the microscale mesh (a) and the scaled error distribution (d). Lastly, the maximum absolute error location is visible in (e). The GNN result is reconstructed from the union of multiple patch predictions where only the ROI is extracted.

(a) FEA

(b) Scaled Error

(c) Location of max error

Figure 12: In subfigure (a) we can see the microscale Von Mises stress distribution as calculated by FEA. In subfigure (b) we can see the scaled error distribution. Lastly, we can also see the maximum absolute error location in (c).

(a) FEA

(b) Scaled Error

(c) Location of max error

Figure 13: In subfigure (a) we can see the microscale Von Mises stress distribution as calculated by FEA. In subfigure (b) we can see the scaled error distribution. Lastly, we can also see the location of the two highest absolute error values in (c).

Figure 14: In subfigure (a) we can see the microscale Von Mises stress distribution as calculated by FEA. In subfigure (b) we can see the scaled error distribution. Lastly, we can also see the location of the two highest absolute error values in (c).

(a) FEA

(b) Scaled Error

(c) Location of max error

Figure 15: In subfigure (a) we can see the microscale Von Mises stress distribution as calculated by FEA. In subfigure (b) we can see the scaled error distribution. Lastly, we can also see the maximum absolute error location in (c).

5 Evaluate GNN performance using stress triaxiality

In this section we evaluate the performance of the GNN using the triaxiality instead of the Von Mises stress. The triaxiality reflects the ratio between the isotropic (or spherical) part of the stress tensor, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{sph}$, and the anisotropic (or deviatoric) part of the stress tensor, \mathbf{s} . The triaxiality, η , can be calculated as:

$$\eta = \frac{\sqrt{2} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{sph}}{3 \|\mathbf{s}\|} \quad (3)$$

where the isotropic and anisotropic stress parts can be expressed as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{sph} = \sqrt{3} \sigma_m \quad (4)$$

$$\|\mathbf{s}\| = \sqrt{2J_2} \quad (5)$$

where σ_m and J_2 read as, respectively

$$\sigma_m = \frac{1}{3} \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}) \quad (6)$$

$$J_2 = \frac{1}{2} [\text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}^2) - \frac{1}{3} \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma})^2] \quad (7)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor in a coordinate system aligned with the principal axes of the stress state.

We conduct a similar study as the one conducted in [section 5.3.3] of the main work (but using the triaxiality instead of the Von Mises stress) and we have reached the same conclusions. We report the error in the triaxiality stress in the ROI of the patches between the FEA calculations and the GNN predictions. Specifically, we are interested in the maximum absolute error of the log triaxiality stress, defined for every ROI as $error_{\text{triaxiality}} = \max(|\log_{\text{triaxiality}_{\text{FEA}}} - \log_{\text{triaxiality}_{\text{NN}}}|)$, where $\log_{\text{triaxiality}_{\text{FEA}}} = \log_{10}(|\text{triaxiality}_{\text{FEA}}|)$ and $\log_{\text{triaxiality}_{\text{NN}}} = \log_{10}(|\text{triaxiality}_{\text{NN}}|)$. From [Fig 16] we can see that the mean error decreases as more data are added in the training set. We also give some insights for the distribution of the error across the patches instead of just showing the mean value. To this end we provide box plots for the relative error [Fig 17]. We can see that as more data are added, not only the mean error but also the error values that correspond to the high error points decrease.

Figure 16: In this diagram we see the mean error over all the patches between the triaxiality stress in the ROI of the patches as calculated by FEA and as predicted from the GNN, $\text{mean}(\text{error}_{\text{triaxiality}})$. The x axis corresponds to the number of data used to train the GNNs. The figure is plotted in a log-log scale.

Figure 17: In the diagram on the left (a) we see 5 box plots for the error between the triaxiality stress in the ROI of the patches as calculated by FEA and as predicted from the GNN, $\text{error}_{\text{triaxiality}}$. Each box plot is defined by 5 numbers. The 2 whiskers at the top and bottom correspond to the 95th and 5th percentiles respectively. The top and bottom limits of the box correspond to the 75th and 25th percentiles respectively. Finally, the yellow line corresponds to the mean of the data. Each box plot corresponds to a GNN trained with different number of data. In the diagram on the right (b) we can see the same box plots without the outliers so that the trend is clearly visible. Each box plot corresponds to 1,000 points.

References

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